

USE OF MODERN INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING ENGLISH

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Annotation: This article highlights the importance given to foreign languages in the Republic of Uzbekistan and the innovative technologies needed to study them.

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After the independence of our country, the interest in teaching foreign languages has grown and many opportunities have been created for young people. As the first President Islam Karimov said, "At present, great importance is attached to the teaching of foreign languages in our country. This, of course, is not in vain. There is no need to underestimate the importance of perfect knowledge of foreign languages for our countries, which today are striving to take their rightful place in the world community, for our people, who are building their great future in cooperation with our foreign partners. " As a logical continuation of these ideas, the Presidential Decree "On Measures to Further Improve the System of Teaching Foreign Languages" adopted on December 10, 2012, expanded the opportunities for learning foreign languages.

Today, foreign language skills are becoming an integral part of vocational education. Specialists in various fields have a high level of cooperation with foreign partners, so they have a high demand for language learning. In modern society, foreign languages are becoming an important part of vocational education. Such knowledge is first acquired by people in schools, colleges, high schools, and later in institutes, training courses, or by familiarizing themselves with basic information sets that help them learn a foreign language independently. Today there is a large collection of teaching materials for people with different levels of language skills.

Success in achieving this goal depends on the practical methods and skills of teachers. The ability to use information technology and modern teaching methods helps to quickly grasp new materials.¹ By combining different methods, a teacher is able to solve specific curricula. In this regard, teachers and students need to become familiar with modern methods of teaching foreign languages. As a result, you will be able to choose the most effective way to achieve your goals. Using a variety of teaching and learning methods can be

effective. Teaching takes place in small steps and is based on the student's existing knowledge system.² As time goes on, innovation in every field increases. There are also different styles of language teaching. When teaching English, it is best to use step-by-step instructions, depending on the age and level of the learner. Students are divided into groups based on elementary education, intermediate education, and advanced education. A special program will be developed by the teacher for each stage.

New methods and requirements for foreign language teaching in the country have been developed in accordance with the Recommendations of the European Framework for Assessment of Knowledge and Skills of Foreign Language Teachers (CEFR). According to him, textbooks have been created for students of secondary schools and vocational colleges. In accordance with these requirements, classrooms are equipped with stands and new information and communication technologies. The demand for learning a foreign language is growing day by day. Foreign language science is divided into four aspects (reading, reading, listening comprehension and speaking), each of which provides specific concepts and skills. Educational technology is the effective use of modern information technology in the educational process. It also aims to improve the quality and effectiveness of education through the introduction of modern innovative technologies in the educational process. In particular, there are several advantages to using such information and communication technologies in learning a foreign language. The role of modern technology in language learning and teaching is invaluable. The use of technology is useful in every aspect of learning a foreign language (reading, reading, listening and speaking). For example, to listen and understand, of course, it is impossible to do this process without a computer, player, CDs. Listening is one of the most important parts of language learning. This requires the student to pay attention to the speaker's pronunciation, grammatical rules, vocabulary, and meanings at the same time. An important factor in the use of modern technologies in education is the ability of students to know and use information and communication technologies. Teaching and learning a foreign language using modern technology is one of the most effective ways.

In this process, including:

- When using computers, the student can watch and listen to videos, demonstrations, dialogues, movies or cartoons in a foreign language;
- It is possible to listen and watch radio broadcasts in foreign languages and TV programs;

- use of tape recorders and cassettes, which are more traditional methods;
- CD players are available. The use of these tools will make the process of learning a foreign language more interesting and effective for students.

Today, interactive games are becoming a tradition in schools. It is well known that a variety of games help students demonstrate their abilities, focus, increase their knowledge and skills, and become stronger.

The basis of the use of game technology is the activity that activates and accelerates the student. According to psychologists, the psychological mechanisms of playful activity are based on the fundamental needs of the individual to express themselves, to find a stable place in life, to self-manage, to realize their potential. At the heart of any game should be the generally accepted principles and tactics of education. Learning games should be based on the subjects. During the games, the student is more interested in this activity than in a normal lesson and works more comfortably. It should be noted that the game is, first of all, a way of teaching. Students are interested in playful lessons, they strive to win, and the teacher uses them to educate the student. The student is interested in believing that he or she can play, speak, listen, understand, and write in English.

As we have seen, each innovative technology has its own set of advantages. All of these methods involve collaboration between teacher and student, active participation of the student in the educational process. Modern language teaching focuses on shaping a more cultured individual who has the skills to self-analyze and systematize new knowledge. Innovative methods are an integral part of modernizing the entire system. With this in mind, teachers can become acquainted with the most advanced approaches and then combine them and use them in their work to achieve significant growth in the education system. Many organizations are moving to a new level, using multimedia capabilities to send and receive information. The use of computers and other devices determines the success of the whole educational process.

Adequate attention should be paid to the formation of speech skills and the development of social resilience in educational training. In addition, the success of any lesson in education depends in many ways on the proper organization of the lessons. The lesson should be based on the creative collaboration of teacher and student. Only then will students be able to think independently and develop their will. In short, the use of innovative methods in English lessons develops students' logical thinking skills, fluency, and the ability to respond quickly and accurately. Such methods stimulate the student's desire for knowledge. The

student strives to be well prepared for the lessons. This makes students active participants in the learning process. As the education system sets itself the task of nurturing a free-thinking, wellrounded, mature person, in the future we, future teachers, will contribute to the more perfect development of ways to effectively use innovative technologies. possible.

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